

APPLICATION OF ADVANCED CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITES TO A TIP TURBINE STRUCTURE OF THE ATREX ENGINE

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SUMMARY: A feasibility study was carried out to apply a carbon/carbon (C/C) composite to a turbine disk of Air-Turbo-Ram-Jet engine. The C/C composite has not been successfully applied to such a primary structure subjected to a dynamic load. The optimum design of the turbine disk made of C/C composites was explored in two kinds of structure, i.e., monolithic and joined. The monolithic structure was assumed to be composed of three-dimensionally reinforced (3D) fabrics and the joined structure divided into three components. Through the discussion, the joined structure was shown to be superior to the monolithic structure. It is due to the reason that in the joined structure the optimum arrangement of reinforcing fiber can be easily made obeying the stress distribution in the turbine disk.

KEYWORDS: carbon/carbon (C/C) composite, air-turbo-ram-jet engine, optimum design, dove tail joint

INTRODUCTION

A development study on an ATREX engine, air turbo ram jet with the expander cycle, is now under way in the Institute of Space and Astronautical Science (Japan). The ATREX engine is a combined cycle engine performing like a turbojet engine at a subsonic to Mach 2 flight and a fun-boost ramjet in the flight of Mach 2 to 6 and is planned to be applied to a propulsion system of a fly-back booster of a TSTO (Two stage to orbit) space plane. The structure of the ATREX engine under development is schematically shown in Fig.1, where main feature is that the expander cycle is adopted to improve high speed efficiency and the tip-turbine configuration is employed so as to provide compactness and light weight of the turbo machinery.

This engine is estimated to possess sufficient effective thrust up to Mach 6 at 35 km altitude. The 1/4-scale model of the ATREX engine, outer diameter of tip-turbine being about 400mm, has been fabricated using refractory metals and performance of it was tested under the sea level-static condition (Step I in Fig.1). It was reported that satisfactory performance was obtained in preliminary tests, which demonstrated that the flight speed of the Mach 6 is possibly realized [1]. Requirement for the tip-turbine structure of ATREX, shown as the shaded region in Fig.1 and in detail in Fig.2, is extremely severe due to high

temperature environment up to 1500°C and hard loading condition by centrifugal force. Because of this, conventional metallic material, such as super alloy, cannot be applied without a cooling system.

Fig.1 An explanatory diagram of the ATREX engine mechanism.

Fig.2 A schematic drawing of the turbine disk for the ATREX engine.

While the tip-turbine structure was made of heat resistant super alloy in the preliminary stage due to low temperature environment in this stage, advanced Carbon-Carbon Composite (ACC) is attempted to be employed as the material for the tip turbine structure. Since the ACCs appears to be only material that simultaneously possess low density about 1.8 g/cm³ and superior mechanical properties, high stiffness and strength, at elevated temperature more than 2000°C [2,3], utilization of the ACC is regarded as an indispensable factor to attain the flight speed of Mach 6.

Table 1 Environmental condition of the ATREX engine.

Turbine Type		Tip Turbine
Tip Speed (m/s)	Turbine	600 ~ 700
	Fan	500 ~600
Fan Inlet Diameter (mm)		300 ~ 600
Fan Inlet Air Temp. (K)		1300
Turbine Inlet H2 Temp. (K)		1800
Heat Exchanger Inlet Combustion Gas Temp. (K)		2700
Heat Exchanger Wall Temp. (K)		2000
Cycle		about 60 min. x1

As shown in Fig.2, the turbine disk has a complex shape, that consists of 2 rings, the turbine ring and the fan disk, and the fan blade connecting the 2 rings. This type of a shape is ordinary regarded as rather difficult to form by use of a continuous fiber reinforced composite material. This is due to difficulty to arrange fiber directions optimally in accordance with varying loading directions from place to place. Thus in this paper, emphasis will be placed upon how to place reinforcing fibers and how to integrate the optimally designed components into the tip turbine disk system.

STRESSES INDUCED IN TURBINE DISK

The most severe stress appeared in the turbine disk is estimated to be that due to the centrifugal force. In Fig.3 the highest stresses in the individual components, the turbine ring, the fan, and the fan disk, of the turbine disk induced by the centrifugal force are shown as a function of the rotation speed of the outer fan tip. In the calculation of Fig.3, the stress transfer between the individual elements was neglected, in other words, the stresses shown in Fig.3 is the maximum tensile stress in the each component when they rotate independently in the own place. It is obvious from this figure that the hoop stress in the turbine ring is highest and the value of the stress is about 560 MPa at 440m/s, which is the rotation speed when the flight speed is supposed to be Mach 6.

Fig.3 The maximum stress induced in each component of the turbine disk as a function of the fan tip speed.

In addition to the centrifugal force, thermal mismatch stresses should be induced due to temperature distribution of in the turbine disk. For instance in the Mach 6 flight condition, temperatures of the tip turbine, the outer tip of the fan, and the fan disk are estimated to be 1500°C, 1200°C, and 800°C, respectively. In the case of a turbine made of nickel base super alloy whose coefficient of thermal expansion, CTE, is about 8×10^{-6} , thermal mismatch displacement between the fan and the turbine ring in the radial direction yields thermal stress of about 800 MPa. On the other hand, for the case of the ACCs the CTE is extremely low ($-1 \times 10^{-6} \sim 1 \times 10^{-6} /K$), though the CTEs of laminate ACCs along the out of plane direction is

relatively high ($4 \times 10^{-6} \sim 8 \times 10^{-6} /K$). Thus the effect of thermal mismatch stress can be neglected.

PROPERTIES OF ACC

Strength and toughness of the ACCs ordinary increase with increase of temperature up to about $2500^{\circ}C$. Hence we can conservatively estimate applicability of the ACCs from the mechanical properties at the room temperature. Recently strength of a high performance ACC improved rapidly, for instance with the room temperature strength for unidirectionally reinforced one; 1400MPa and a cross ply laminate; 700 to 800 MPa [3,4]. Thus from the comparison of the predicted maximum stress of 560 MPa in Fig.3 and the above-mentioned strength of the ACCs, it can be concluded that the ACCs possesses sufficient capability to sustaine the load required for the ATREX turbine disk.

However, the ACCs have well known two kinds of drawback. First one is low strength of interlaminar. For example, interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of a unidirectional and cross ply ACCs are 20~30 MPa and 10~20 MPa, respectively. Since complex tri-axial stresses distribution is anticipated to be induced in the turbine disk, It is concluded that three-dimensional reinforcement [5] is indispensable for the ACC application.

The other problem is low oxidation resistance of the ACC in high temperature oxidizing environment higher than $500^{\circ}C$. It is established fact that thermal barrier coating of SiC and vitreous crack shielding is effective especially against short period and low times of heat cycle oxidation in the temperature range up to $1700^{\circ}C$ [6,7]. Thus the SiC coating is assumed to be applied to the region of the fan and fun disk. For the outer side of the turbine ring and the tip turbine, the SiC coating can be omitted, because atmosphere of them is pure hydrogen, and to hydrogen, ACCs possess sufficient environmental resistance even in elevated temperature.

CONFIGURATION OF TIP TURBINE STRUCTURE

The load and shape of the turbine disk are essentially axi-symmetric. Therefore it is not difficult to estimate stress distribution roughly and locations of stress concentration in the turbine disk. High values of tensile stress are predicted in the turbine ring in circumferential direction and fans and their roots in the radial direction. To reinforce these regions and directions, two types of configurations made of the ACCs will be explored, i.e., monolithic and joined Structures.

Monolithic Structure

As for a monolithic structure, three-dimensionally woven (3D) fabrics reinforced in the directions of r, q, and z as schematically shown in Fig.6 are considered to be a most promising material as a reinforcement of the ACCs, in which z axis coincides with rotational axis. In this configuration, a thick circular disk made of the ACC may be firstly formed. Then the disk is machined into the shape of the turbine disk by cutting tools.

One of difficulties encountered in the monolithic structure is that high value of tensile stress is anticipated in the fan due to the load transfer from the expanding turbine ring by the centrifugal force. This stress appears due to variation of the centrifugal force with the radial

position, i.e., difference between large radial displacement of the turbine ring and small displacement of the fan.

Fig.4 A3 – dimensionally reinforced fabrics for the turbine disk and its texture

It can be minimized if the radial displacement of the turbine ring can be suppressed for example by increasing Young's modulus of the turbine ring. Figure 7 represents the effect of Young's modulus on the tensile load of the fan blade. In the figure 1xE, 3xE, 5xE, and 10xE stand for the cases of Young's modulus ratio of the turbine ring to the fan being 1, 3, 5 and 10, respectively. It is obvious from this figure that the fan stress drastically decreases with increase of the turbine ring modulus and, when the ratio equals to 5, the stress transfer from the turbine ring to the fan blade becomes negligible. However in the monolithic structure, volume fraction of the reinforcing fiber cannot be controlled freely so as to control the Young's modulus.

Fig.5 The effect of Young's modulus ratio of the turbine disk on the transfer load from the turbine ring to the fan blade.

As shown in Fig.4, the maximum stress appears in the turbine ring, and this stress is tensile and in the circumferential direction. Hence, in the turbine ring heavy reinforcement must be placed in the hoop direction to sustain centrifugal force as well as to cancel load transfer from

the turbine ring to the fan. On the hand, the heaviest reinforcement in radial direction is required in the fan and nearly isotropic one in the fan disk. Thus roughly speaking, ideal reinforcing directions are hoop in the turbine ring, radial in the fan, and quasi-isotropic in the fan disk, respectively. Among them the reinforcement of the turbine ring takes priority of others as demonstrated by Fig.4.

Fig.6 Volume fraction of hoop fiber in the 3-dimensionally reinforced fabric for the turbine disk.

In the meanwhile, fabrics makers say that from the view point of restriction on fabricating 3D fabrics the volume fraction of the hoop fibers in the 3D fabrics for the turbine ring is at the utmost set to 45%. With this volume fraction in turbine ring, it is not difficult to get three times difference of the fiber volume fractions between the turbine ring in the hoop direction and the fan blade in the radial direction. The ACC using the preform shown in Fig.8 has been thus fabricated, i.e. to obtain three times of the volume fraction difference, volume fraction of hoop fiber V_{fq} is intentionally varied as shown in the figure, and machined into simplified monolithic structure model as shown in Fig.9. High speed rotation test will be carried out to ensure potential of monolithic structure.

In the monolithic structure, there is one more difficulty being necessary to be overcome. While the fan is twisted as shown in Fig.3, the radial reinforcing fiber is straight. Therefore the radial reinforcing fibers in the fan are actually cut into short fibers and radial strength in the fan must be reduced greatly. In order to get over this problem, the following two countermeasures are being explored.

To develop 3D-fabrics with the radial fiber curved along the twisted fan.

To make the fan thicker so as to maintain sufficient strength.

Joined Structure

The other configuration is a joined structure. In this configuration, the fan disk, fan blades, and turbine ring + tip turbine blades, shown in Fig.3, are first formed separately and then the fabricated each component is to be assembled into the tip turbine disk structure in the order shown in Fig.10. For this structure, strength of each components can be easily optimized in

accordance with each stress distribution, because fiber orientations and volume fractions can be easily optimized due to simplicity of component shapes.

Fig.7 A simplified model for the monolithic turbine disk made of 3-dimensionally reinforced ACC.

In order to assemble the turbine disk structure efficiently, two types of joint configurations are attempted to be employed as shown in Fig.11. One of the joints is a dovetail joint between the fan blade and the fan disk, and the other is a pin joint between the fan blade and the turbine ring. Simplified component tests and analytical studies have been carried out on both type of joints.

Fig.8 Assembling procedure for the joint tip turbine disk.

Fig.9 An schematic drawing of two types of joint adopted in the turbine disk of the joined structure

Dovetail Joints

Both of analytical and experimental studies have been carried out on simplified models of the dovetail joint to optimize the dovetail shape and reinforcing directions in ACC.

As a first step analysis, FEM study of the dovetail joint was carried out to clarify the relation between stress distribution and the shape of the joint for laminate type ACC using the two dimensional anisotropic analysis model as shown in Fig.12(a) under loading condition of 440m/s rotation. From these studies, it was shown that the ACC dovetail joint with lower shoulder angle, for example 30° , has higher load bearing capability. But as shown in Fig.12(b), which is typical results of interlaminar shear stress induced in the dovetail, maximum interlaminar shear stress is 90 MPa at the shoulder that an arrow indicate in the figure. Because it is about nine times higher than ILSS of laminate type ACC, it is concluded that laminate type ACC is not adequate for the dovetail material.

Tensile tests of a simplified dovetail joint model made of three dimensionally reinforced (3D) ACC have been carried out as a function of shoulder angle and root curvature to optimize the shape of the dovetail configuration as shown in Fig.12. Figure 13 shows preliminary results of tensile test for dovetail made of 3D ACC. As shown in the figure, maximum load is 7.2 kN. Assuming the 1/4 scale tip turbine structure model (diameter of f400 mm at fan tip), load bearing capacity in actual dovetail made of 3D ACC can be estimated as 106 kN. Considering loading conditions in actual structure of 73 kN at rotation speed of 440 m/s, experimental results suggest that 3D ACCs are possibly applicable to dovetail joints of the ATR engine, at least assuming maximum load can be applied for design. Further experimental and analytical studies are required to clarify the design limit for 3D ACCs and to optimize the shape of dovetail, because subcritical damages will be introduced during loading before final fracture.

*Fig.10 The FEM analysis of the dovetail joint.
 (a) An analytical model,
 (b) A calculation results for the interlaminar shear stress.*

Pin Joints

The other is a pin joint between the fan blade and the turbine ring (Fig.11). This joint transfers the weak circumferential force but doesn't the radial force. Main problem of this joined structure is to prevent reduction of turbine ring strength. As a rule of a jet engine, holes should not be made in the turbine ring because burst rotation speeds of the turbine ring tend to be drastically lowered due to stress concentration appeared around the hole. Thus detailed study on a relaxation measure of the stress concentration around the joint holes is required to materialize this structure. Actually, the tensile test of ACC plates with a hole were carried out to rationalize the joint behavior between the fan blade and the turbine ring using specimens shown in Fig15. Typical results of tensile tests are shown in Fig.16, where stress concentrations were calculated as ratio of fracture stress averaged over minimum net section of specimen with a hole to the fracture strength of smooth specimen. For comparison, analytical results by FEM were also calculated assuming fracture will occur when the maximum strength in the specimen reaches fracture strength of smooth specimen. From these results, it was concluded that fracture stress of specimen with a hole was insensitive to stress concentration around a hole, and thus pin joint between the fan blade and the turbine ring was regarded as a quite effective structure for the case of ACCs.

Fig.11 A test configuration for the measurement of dove tail strength

Fig.12 An Load-displacement curve of in the tensile test of the dovetail joint made of 3D ACC..

An unsettled factor peculiar to the joined structure is vibration induced by asymmetric displacement of the turbine ring during high speed rotation. The pin joints automatically tend to suppress non-axi-symmetric displacement because stiffness of the joint pin and the fan blade prevent the asymmetric displacement. However the region of rotation speed of turbine disk, where this mechanism is effective, is not clear and a simple model experiment is now in preparation.

Comparison of load bearing capability between the monolithic and joined structures leads to a tentative conclusion that the joined structure is superior to the monolithic structure, though uncertainty concerning vibration of the turbine ring is still exist..

HIGH SPEED ROTATION TEST

High speed rotation tests have been also carried out to confirm the stress distribution and the failure criteria of the tip turbine structure under rotation. Fig.17 represents schematic view of the rotation burst tester derived by an air turbine, made by Maruwa electric Co., that have the maximum rotation speed, 100000 r.p.m. In this tester, telemeters and high speed cameras are mounted to measure strain distribution and fracture initiation patterns of the rotating disk. During the rotation test, the chamber, in which the specimen is set, is evacuated by a rotary pump.

Fig.13 Stress concentration in the tensile test of the ACC specimen with a hole.

The test on a flat ACC disk with the quasi-isotropic stacking sequence of carbon fiber resulted in the peripheral velocity of the fan equal to 427 m/s at the burst point of the ACC disk. The fracture pattern of the disk specimen is shown in Fig.18. The fractured specimen was collected by thick felt sheets and rubber tire. Comparison between the results from the rotation test and that of static tensile test implied that the failure of ACC during rotation test occurred obeying the average stress condition over the radius of the disk rather than the maximum stress condition. In the next step, a high speed rotation test of simplified turbine models will be performed to explore further efficient structures.

Fig.14 A schematic drawing of the spin burst tester.

FURTHER APPLICATION OF ACCS

Almost all the components of ATREX engine are to be exposed to high temperature environment as shown in Fig.19. It is obvious from this figure that the down stream region of engine becomes extremely high temperature. As shown in Fig.20 there is no other material exhibiting high strength in the temperature range higher than 1200° C. Thus to lower the weight of the whole engine system by minimizing introduction of a cooling system, utmost application of the ACCs is preferred. In our project, the next item to examine the ACC application is chosen to be the heat exchanger. Difficulties encountered in the ACC application of the heat exchanger are extremely high temperature in oxidation environment

and an extremely complex shape. By application of ACC to the turbine disk and the heat exchanger, weight reduction compared with an all-metal engine is estimated to be 35kg in the 1/4 scale model.

Table2 Stress concentration in turbine disk models.

Models	Elements	Average stress	Concentration points	Stress concentration
Monolithic structure	Ring (σ_{θ})	126 (a1)	221 (a2)	1.8 (a2/a1)
	Fan (σ_r)	74 (b1)	103 (b2)	1.4 (b2/b1)
Joined structure	Ring (σ_{θ})	323 (c1)	790 (c2)	2.4 (c2/c1)
	Fan (σ_r)	199 (d1)	312 (d2)	1.6 (d2/d1)

*1 σ_{θ} : Circumferential stress (MPa), σ_r :Radial stress (MPa)

*2 Rotating speeds: Monolithic 30,000rpm, Joined 30,600rpm

Table3 Measured strains and estimated fracture rotation speeds.

Specimens	Elements	Measured strain (5,000rpm)	Failure rotating speeds (2,000 $\mu\epsilon$)	Failure circumferential speeds
Monolithic structure	Ring (ϵ_{θ})	24.6 $\mu\epsilon$	45,083 rpm	472 m/s
	Fan (ϵ_r)	61.4 $\mu\epsilon$	28,536 rpm	298 m/s
3D-Ring	Ring (ϵ_{θ})	24.4 $\mu\epsilon$	45,267 rpm	474 m/s

*1 Measured points: center of elements

*2 Circumferential speeds : calculation based on specimen diameter ϕ 200mm

*3 ϵ_{θ} : Circumferential strain, ϵ_r : Radial strain

CONCLUSION

In order to apply ACC to the tip turbine structure, feasibility study was carried out on the two types of configurations, those were the monolithic structure and the joined structure.

Comparison of load bearing capacity by the stress analysis and component tests for both configurations, it is tentatively concluded that the joined structure is superior to the monolithic structure.

Further study is needed to optimize shape and arrangement of reinforcing fiber directions. Furthermore, vibration in the joined structure should be evaluated for materializing tip turbine structure.

REFERENCES

- N. Tanatsugu et.al.,” Development Study on ATREX Engine for Future Space Plane” , 19th ISTS, 1994-5 Yokohama, in printing.
- G. Savage, “ Carbon-Carbon Composites” , Chapmanhall, 1993.
- C. R. Thomas, “ Essentials of Carbon-Carbon Composites” , Roy. Soc. Chem., 1993.
- J. E. Sheehan, “ Carbon-Carbon Materials and Composites” , NASA Ref. Pub., Chap.8, pp.223-266, 1992.
- T. W. Chou, F. K. Ko, “ Textile Structural Composites” , Composite Material Series Vol.3, Elsevier, 1989.